

A New Empirical Equation for the Determination of Dipole Moment in Solution

S. R.M. M. MEYYAPPAN & N. ARUNACHALAM

Department of Physics, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar, Tamilnadu

Received 3 February 1972

Jenkins¹ suggested that $P_{2\infty}$, the total molecular polarization of solute at infinite dilution, is a linear function of $1/\epsilon_1$ while measuring the dipole moment of nitrobenzene in different solvents. He gave an equation

$$P_{2\infty} = A \pm B/\epsilon_1$$

where A and B are constants and ϵ_1 is the dielectric constant of the non-polar solvent. This expression seems to hold good over a considerable range of ϵ_1 . Generally this solvent effect is attributed to the polarization induced in the molecules of the solvent by the electric fields of the molecular dipoles of the solute. Hence if the solvents enter into inter-molecular exchange with the solute, the dipole moment then measured no longer corresponds to the true value of the dissolved substance. In order to obtain the true values of dipole moment, we proposed a new empirical equation for a system where strong or specific interactions are absent.

The new empirical equation which correlates $P_{2\infty}$, the apparent molecular polarization of solute at infinite dilution, with the dielectric constants of the polar solute and non-polar solvent is given below

$$P_{2\infty} = P_1 + (P_2 - P_1) \frac{\epsilon_2 + 2}{\epsilon_1 + 2}$$

where P_1 and P_2 represent the molar polarization of solvent and solute having dielectric constant ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 respectively.

Using this empirical equation, the apparent molecular polarization at infinite dilution, of a number of pure polar molecules have been calculated at 25° by assuming benzene as solvent molecule. The dipole moment μ_B is derived from the following general expression

$$\mu_B = 0.0128 \sqrt{(P_{2\infty} - R_D)T}$$

where R_D is the polarization due to distortion and T is the absolute temperature at which the measurements have been made. The results of calculations are reported in Table 1. To compare the dipole moment, the values taken from the 'Tables of Experimental Dipole Moments' are used².

TABLE 1

Comparison of the dipole moments (in Debye Units) with the experimental values

Polar solute	ϵ_2	P_{200}	μ_B calculated	μ_B Expt.	μ_{liq}
Cyclohexene	2.2200	29.226	0.33	—	0.28
Ethyl benzene	2.4008	38.868	0.39	0.35	0.37
Triethylamine	2.4222	45.697	0.75	0.80	0.75
Butyric acid	2.9495	38.166	0.88	0.94	1.23
Furan	2.9498	28.805	0.71	0.71	—
Propionic acid	3.3722	34.567	0.91	0.89	1.23
Anisole	4.3308	71.480	1.34	1.30	1.22
Chloroform	4.7992	55.008	1.28	1.22	1.10
Bromobenzene	5.3982	88.218	1.63	1.52	1.54
Chlorobenzene	5.6212	89.216	1.56	1.58	1.54
Methyl acetate	6.6721	79.745	1.74	1.77	1.74

Dielectric constants of the substances were measured at 25° using a WTW heterodyne dipolemeter. The refractive indices were determined at 25° using Abbe's refractometer. Substances were purified by standard methods. Correction for the contribution of the distortion polarization is applied from R_D values. It is found that the values of dipole moments calculated from this empirical equation are in good agreement with the experimentally observed values. The dipole moments of the solutes in the liquid state (μ_{liq}) are also given in the last column in Table 1.

REFERENCES

1. H. O. Jenkins, *Nature*, 1934, **133**, 106.
2. 'Tables of Experimental Dipole Moments', A. L. McClellan, W. H. Freeman and Company, (San Francisco and London), (1963).